

Third wave : The wave appeared on the potential axis in the voltage range -0.84 to -1.29 V vs SCE. Semi-logarithmic analysis of the wave reveals that the wave is irreversible. The limiting current varied linearly with concentration of the hydrazone and with square-root of the mercury column height indicating that the wave is diffusion-controlled. It is reported⁶ that imines ($R^1R^2C=NH$) undergo hydration to give the electro-inactive species [$R^1R^2C(OH)NH_2$]. Hence the third wave is attributed to the reduction of the amide (II) to the corresponding primary alcohol.

Cyclic voltammetric studies :

Cyclic voltammetric studies substantiate the polarographic studies (Fig. 1).

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Studies on Inorganic Ion-exchangers. Part-2. Preparation, Properties and Applications of Zirconium(IV) Selenite

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THE synthesis and ion-exchange properties of inorganic materials have been extensively studied¹. Although a large number of zirconium based ion-exchangers having different anionic part have been studied, no information is available about zirconium(IV) selenite. This paper reports the synthesis, characterisation and ion-exchange behaviour and the effect of γ -irradiation on zirconium(IV) selenite.

Experimental

Zirconium oxychloride and sodium selenite (Loba) were used. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Synthesis : Zirconium(IV) selenite was prepared by mixing aqueous solutions of sodium selenite and zirconyl oxychloride in different concentration, pH and mixing ratios (Table 1). The dried product was converted into colourless H^+ -form by treatment with 1.0 M HNO_3 in the usual manner.

The exchanger (200 mg) was calcined at $850-900^\circ$ to get zirconium oxide (ZrO_2) and from it the weight of Zr was determined². Se was determined as free metal³. The mole ratio is given in Table 1. It was found to be stable in 1.0 M solutions of HCl, H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , ethanol and 0.01 M NaOH.

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF SYNTHESIS AND ION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF ZIRCONIUM(IV) SELENITE

Sample no.	Mixing ratio	Concn. of reagents (M)		pH	Mole ratio	i.e.c. in meq/g for Na^+	i.e.c. for irradiated sample meq/g
		Zr ^{IV}	SeO ₃				
1	1 : 2	0.05	0.1	1.8	1 : 1.2	0.38	—
2	1 : 1	0.05	0.05	1.0	1 : 1.12	0.5	—
3	1 : 2	0.1	0.1	0.85	1 : 2	0.8	0.79
4	1 : 1	0.05	0.05	0.0	1 : 1	0.2	—

A glass-column (i.d. 1.1 cm) was used for column operation. The zirconium(IV) selenite (H^+ -form) (1 g) was taken in the column and the flow rate was initially maintained at 1 ml min^{-1} . A Global DPA-500 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Ion-exchange capacity : The exchange capacity of the material (H^+ -form) was determined by standard method⁴. The strong acid capacities are expressed in terms of meq g^{-1} of the dry samples before and after γ -irradiations (a dose of 100 Mrad at a dose rate of 0.2 Mrad h^{-1}) (Table 1).

Heat treatment :

Sample no. 3 (Table 1) was heated for 6 h each at different temperatures in a thermostatically controlled hot air-oven maintained ($\pm 0.5^\circ$) at desired temperature. The ion-exchange capacity of the heat treated samples was then determined. The effect of temperature upon ion-exchange capacity is presented in Fig. 1. The effect of ionic radii on the exchange capacity is given in Table 2.

Distribution coefficient : The distribution coefficient (K_d) for metal ions taken in demineralised water was determined on Zr^{IV} selenite (sample no. 3)⁴. The cation-exchange loading for the system was less than 3% of the apparent ion-exchange capacity. The following equation was used for calculations,

$$K_d = \frac{I-F}{F} \frac{20}{0.1}$$

NOTES

Fig. 1. Effect of heating upon ion-exchange capacity (I.E.C.) of zirconium(IV) selenite.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SIZE AND CHARGE OF EXCHANGING ION ON EXCHANGE CAPACITY

Exchanging ion	Ionic radii Å	Exchange capacity meq/g
Li	0.60	0.25
Na	0.95	0.80
K	1.33	0.85
Ba ^{II}	1.85	0.90
Sr ^{II}	1.18	0.72
Ca ^{II}	0.99	0.70

where, I is the volume of EDTA solution consumed by the original cation solution and F the volume of EDTA solution consumed after equilibrium. The total volume was 20 ml and the amount of exchanger being 0.1 g. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3— K_d VALUES (ml g^{-1}) OF METAL ION IN ZIRCONIUM(IV) SELENITE DRIED AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Cation	Taken as	K_d ml g^{-1}	K_d (ml g^{-1}) of irradiated sample
Zn ^{II}	Sulphate	4.88	4.7
Mg ^{II}	Chloride	1.01	1.00
Ca ^{II}	Chloride	6.87	6.5
Pb ^{II}	Nitrate	63.158	63.0
Hg ^{II}	Chloride	0	0
Cd ^{II}	Chloride	9.14	9.00
Sn ^{II}	Chloride	CU ^a	CU ^a
Cu ^{II}	Chloride	15.82	15.75
Co ^{II}	Chloride	0	0
Ni ^{II}	Chloride	0	0
Bi ^{III}	Nitrate	220.45	220.0
Th ^{IV}	Nitrate	128.8	128.8

^aCU=Complete uptake.

Results and Discussion

Various samples of zirconium(IV) selenite have been prepared at different conditions. It is evident from Table 1 that at pH 0.85, the exchanger (sample no. 3) shows maximum ion-exchange capacity and stability, and hence this sample was used for the investigations reported.

The ion-exchange capacity of zirconium(IV) selenite decreases on drying in air for long time and by increase of temperature (Fig. 1). The curve

(Fig. 1) indicates that even on heating the sample at 300°, it still retains some ion-exchange capacity.

The effect of size and charge of the exchanging ion on the ion exchange capacity is shown in Table 2. For alkali and alkaline earth metal ions, the sequence shown by zirconium(IV) selenite is as follows: $\text{K} > \text{Na} > \text{Li}$, $\text{Ba}^{\text{II}} > \text{Sr}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$. In the case of zirconium(IV) selenite the ion-exchange capacity increases with the increase of ionic radii, which is in accordance with theoretical considerations.

The uptake sequence (Table 3) for some metal ions (taken in demineralised water) on zirconium(IV) selenite is as follows: $\text{Sn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Bi}^{\text{III}} > \text{Th}^{\text{IV}} > \text{Pb}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ca}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mg}^{\text{II}} > \text{Hg}^{\text{II}} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$. No physical change takes place when the exchanger is equilibrated with Sn^{II} solution and it is found to be completely adsorbed. It can be seen from Table 3 that there is a large difference in the K_d values of $\text{Bi}^{\text{III}} - \text{Th}^{\text{IV}}$, $\text{Zn}^{\text{II}} - \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{Hg}^{\text{II}} - \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$. The quantitative separations of $\text{Zn}^{\text{II}} - \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{Hg}^{\text{II}} - \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$ were successively carried out on a small column of zirconium(IV) selenite. In all cases the recovery range was 97–100% (Table 4).

TABLE 4—BINARY SEPARATIONS

Mixture	Ion-loaded mg	Recovered mg
Zn ^{II} 0.01 M HNO ₃ + 0.01 M NH ₄ NO ₃	3.40	3.95
Pb ^{II} 0.02 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	5.05	5.05
Cu ^{II} 0.01 M HNO ₃ + 0.01 M NH ₄ NO ₃	3.10	3.00
Pb ^{II} 0.02 M HNO ₃ + 0.05 M NH ₄ NO ₃	5.05	5.05
Hg ^{II} Water of pH 5	2.45	2.45
Pb ^{II} 0.02 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	5.05	5.00
Cd ^{II} 0.01 M HNO ₃	2.80	2.80
Pb ^{II} 0.02 M HNO ₃ + 0.5 M NH ₄ NO ₃	5.05	5.00
Ni ^{II} Water of pH 5	2.90	2.80
Cu ^{II} 0.05 M HNO ₃	3.10	3.10

It has been observed that irradiation has no effect on the ion-exchange capacity or the distribution coefficients.

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